

As Penicillin is a cure for bacterial infection, so Copper is a cure for viral infections

Copper is a metal that is one of the least toxic amongst the metals, to human beings. Absorption of a measured amounts of Copper is usually safe to most people [Pregnant women and people with special medical conditions need to consult with a trustworthy physician]. Some people make colloidal Copper and drink it regularly and claim there are health benefits.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S5lSu_Dsoeg

Copper is a metal that kills/destroys viruses [and bacteria]. Viruses are terminated when coming in contact with Copper. This is scientific knowledge that has been present for a long time but for some reason hasn't been implemented. In the past, there was an intention to coat [cover] many surfaces in hospitals with Copper. In Japan, there is an outline to a central air conditioning system that purifies air from harmful bacteria and viruses. There is an outline for doorknobs made out of Copper, to prevent the [viral] spread of disease. Now there are plans to manufacture face masks with copper coating:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44889521_A_Novel_Anti-Influenza_Copper_Oxide_Containing_Respiratory_Face_Mask

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340264949_Proposal_to_Protect_Face_Masks_from_COVID-19_with_a_Copper_Solution_either_on_an_Outer_Cloth_Mask_or_on_a_Rag_in_a_Paper_Bag

There is a metal alloy- brass, which consists of Copper and Zinc. It is known that when cells have a high concentration of zinc, viruses have trouble replicating [they cannot bind to the cell and insert their RNA for replication]. An anti-malaria drug called Chloroquine boosts zinc cell absorption times 10 of the normal amount, thus it could help treat the virus [covid-19]:

<https://www.clinicaltrialsarena.com/news/coronavirus-covid-19-choroquine-data/>

Is it then more useful to use Brass in order to stop the spread of viruses in the biological system? But Copper has Zinc isotopes in it as well, so maybe 'regular' copper is good enough:

Main isotopes of copper				
Iso- tope	Abun- dance	Half-life ($t_{1/2}$)	Decay mode	Pro- duct
^{63}Cu	69.15%	stable		
^{64}Cu	syn	12.70 h	ϵ	^{64}Ni
			β^-	^{64}Zn
^{65}Cu	30.85%	stable		
^{67}Cu	syn	61.83 h	β^-	^{67}Zn

 Category: Copper

Main isotopes of zinc ($_{30}\text{Zn}$)

Isotope			Decay	
	abundance	half-life ($t_{1/2}$)	mode	product
^{64}Zn	49.2%	stable		
^{65}Zn	syn	244 d	ϵ	^{65}Cu
			γ	—
^{66}Zn	27.7%	stable		
^{67}Zn	4.0%	stable		

Copper and Zinc 'compete' for absorption in the body [when one is absorbed- it hinders the other], so is Brass absorbed efficiently in the body? When using Copper it is probably a good idea to also supplement with Zinc [for instance- inhale copper in the morning, take a Zinc supplement at noon, and inhale Copper in the evening].

Now, there is an attempt to market this anti-malarial drug to the masses, but this drug has side-effects¹ and it is very expensive and will generate a huge income to people of interest. Also- it is unknown how effective this drug is against the virus:

<https://www.bbc.com/news/51980731>

This anti-malarial drug also has mitigating effects against radiation damage:

<https://academic.oup.com/jac/article/70/6/1608/728687>

¹ https://futurism.com/neoscope/hydroxychloroquine-increased-death-risk?mc_eid=868584becd&mc_cid=777e78c4ff

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7624433_Chloroquine-Mediated_Radiosensitization_is_due_to_the_Destabilization_of_the_Lysosomal_Membrane_and_Subsequent_Induction_of_Cell_Death_by_Necrosis

Could it be that this "virus" is only part of the Truth and is hiding some form of radiation poisoning that produces flu-like symptoms?

The current flu disease [covid-19] is a disease of the respiratory kind. It is most effective to breathe vapor in order to spread the anti-viral substance into the body, thru the lungs.

It is possible to make colloidal Copper water thru electrolysis of water: You take 2 copper rods, put them in a water vessel, add a conducting substance [citric acid (lemon)/baking soda], connect an electrode to each rod, and run for however long it takes for the water to reach a blueish sky-like tone. Most people use about 27 volts for a few hours. It is possible to use 3 9V batteries [follow the link to the YouTube video, attached bellow]. In order to make the colloidal copper with small particles, it is best to use higher voltage but not too high a current [amp]. Gently stir the water once in a while. It is also good to change polarity of the electrodes to prevent the solution from dropping oxides to the bottom of the vessel. During the electrolysis, one electrode produces oxygen, and the other Hydrogen [you can see rising bubbles]. It is possible to measure the exact amount of copper in the water using a special instrument. The measurement unit is PPM- Parts per Million. 1 PPM equals to 1 milligram. The daily dose recommended by the mainstream health authorities is 1-10 ml [this is the conservative systemic recommendation]. per day for an adult. Since a conductive substance [baking soda/lemon] is added to the water- it is better to test the water conductivity before starting the electrolysis process, and after, and then calculate the difference. It is possible to make less concentrated colloidal copper of 50-200 PPM for drinking a small amount, or a more concentrated form of 200-600 PPM and boil the liquid

for inhalation. For example, after making colloidal copper of 50 PPM, it is recommended to drink up to about a cup [200 ml] of it per day.

You can drink the water- it is stronger and very bitter [small sips] - this is for when someone needs quick and strong treatment. For a gentler and more gradual treatment: you take the water and boil it [a kettle will do] and use an inhalation system or just the old way of a kettle and a towel- to breathe the vapor in [for maybe 5-10 minutes, use your discretion]. At that temperature, the metal will not go into the vapor phase. The colloidal will crash and you will get a precipitate of the metal. But a smaller [safer] amount of the Copper molecules will go up with the vapor ['Entailment']. Each portion of colloidal water should probably be used only once with this method. This treatment needs to be consistent for a week or so, like the penicillin treatment- it has a cumulative affect. The current recommendation is:

First day: 3 times a day.

Second day: 2 times a day.

Third to Seventh day: 1 time a day.

* Against radiation damage and anti-cancer, the treatment should be continuous and not for only a brief period.

Here is a YouTube video showing how to safely make colloidal silver- the same method can be used for colloidal copper:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lrZC34WspCs&t=324s>

This written paper is a theory. It is yet to be proven or disproven. What I ask is for someone to try to prove/disprove this theory scientifically, in an unbiased way, Truthfully.

The basic experiment is simple:

1. Measure the patient's health condition and viral load.

2. A. Copper/ B. Brass Inhalation for the Patient.

3. Measure the patient's health condition and viral load.

---Analyze the data and the difference between 1 and 3

The writer of this document has been making and using colloidal copper on himself, with [subjective] great improvement in overall sensation and health.

People's lives are at stake. The cure is totally free, a gift of donation [Terumah] to the people of our world.

The author of this document has no conflict of interest- is not receiving money from any institution and has done this research in a totally independent way and with the sole purpose of doing good and helping people.

Reference studies showing the anti-viral properties of Copper:

[Copper against radiation poisoning:](#)

<https://emfacademy.com/copper-block-emf-radiation/>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/srep24234>

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1559325820904547>

<https://skinbiologyscience.hoop.la/topic/copper-peptides-protect-against-uv-radiation>

Copper against cancer:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19355889>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-019-41063-x>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19199864>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23987360_Copper_Complexes_as_Anticancer_Agents

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265346587_Advances_in_Copper_Complexes_as_Anticancer_Agents

<https://www.google.com/search?client=firefox-b-d&q=copper+anti+cancer>

Copper against infections:

<http://theconversation.com/copper-is-great-at-killing-superbugs-so-why-dont-hospitals-use-it-73103>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279889447_Historic_uses_of_copper_compounds_in_medicine

<https://learningenglish.voanews.com/a/copper-kills-viruses-on-contact/3147962.html>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2905157/>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Antimicrobial_properties_of_copper

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Antimicrobial_copper-alloy_touch_surfaces

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3067274/>

<https://www.newsweek.com/copper-hospital-healing-medicine-561715>

<http://sciencenetlinks.com/science-news/science-updates/antibacterial-doorknobs/>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4292492/>

<https://web.archive.org/web/20111123100624/http://www.antimicrobialcopper.com/media/149689/pr811-chilean-subway-installs-antimicrobial-copper.pdf>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/961545/>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Copper_alloys_in_aquaculture

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/Home/Science/Made-in-India-Water-in-brass-vessel-healthy/articleshow/1075915.cms>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9587153/>

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4613-0553-8_11

<https://academic.oup.com/ajcn/article/67/5/1064S/4666232>

<https://lpi.oregonstate.edu/mic/minerals/copper>

Copper against Prions:

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/bi060948r#>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2376760/>

Copper for water purification:

<https://www.copper.org/publications/newsletters/innovations/2000/01/cleanup.html>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3312355/>

<http://recentscientific.com/review-copper-disinfectant-water-purification>

https://www.jstor.org/stable/1630033?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents

<https://food.ndtv.com/health/12-amazing-healing-benefits-of-drinking-water-in-a-copper-vessel-1658134>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0043135414004515>

Copper absorption in the human body

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S002432051400530X>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1550413106002798>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12572674>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12540371>

<https://copperalliance.org.uk/knowledge-base/education/education-resources/copper-essential-human-health/>

“Jerusalem of gold and of Copper and of Light”

“And the yard’s rods, Copper:” Terumah

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ר' ניסן ה'תש"ף